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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
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- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
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- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE AND WORD FORMATION OF ECOTOURISM TERMINOLOGY: A CROSS-LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS WITH REFERENCE TO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This paper analyzes the morphological structure, word-formation patterns, and cross-linguistic adaptation of ecotourism terminology, comparing international standards with the development of the Uzbek language. By examining affixation, compounding, and borrowing, the study emphasizes the need to standardize Uzbek ecotourism terms in order to balance global English-driven terminology with national linguistic identity and cultural accuracy.

Key words: ecotourism, Uzbek language, morphology, word formation, borrowing, translation studies, terminological standardization, local scholarship.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ekoturizm terminologiyasining morfologik tuzilishi, so'z yasalish modellari va kross-lingvistik moslashuvini tahlil qilib, xalqaro standartlarni o'zbek tilining rivojlanishi bilan qiyoslaydi. Affiksatsiya, qo'shma so'z yasalishi va o'zlashmalarni ko'rib chiqish orqali tadqiqot ingliz tili yetakchiligidagi global terminologiyalar bilan milliy lingvistik o'zlik hamda madaniy aniqlik o'rtasidagi muvozanatni saqlash uchun o'zbek ekoturizm terminlarini standartlashtirish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekoturizm, o'zbek tili, morfologiya, so'z yasalishi, o'zlashma, tarjimashunoslik, terminologik standartlashtirish, mahalliy ilmiy tadqiqotlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются морфологическая структура, словообразовательные модели и кросс-лингвистическая адаптация терминологии экотуризма, сопоставляются международные стандарты с развитием узбекского языка. Путём исследования аффиксации, словосложения и заимствования работа подчёркивает необходимость стандартизации узбекских терминов экотуризма для достижения баланса между глобальной англоязычной терминологией, национальной языковой идентичностью и культурной точностью.

Ключевые слова: экотуризм, узбекский язык, морфология, словообразование, заимствование, переводоведение, терминологическая стандартизация, местная научная школа.

INTRODUCTION

With the growing significance of ecotourism in the global community, driven by environmental consciousness and sustainability agendas, its specialized terminology has also been expanding rapidly. According to Fennell, ecotourism can be defined as responsible tourism in the natural environment that not only preserves the environment but also enhances community welfare ^[4]. This definition outlines the semantic field of ecotourism vocabulary. The rapid growth of ecotourism has driven an unprecedented expansion of its specialized terminology, transforming it from niche travel into a complex field at the intersection of ecology, ethics, and economics.

As a "terminological explosion" occurs, precise translation becomes crucial for cross-cultural comprehension, ensuring that sustainability concepts are accurately conveyed rather than lost in translation. Local scholars have also incorporated ecotourism terminology into their research, such as Umida Nigmatullayeva Abdullayeva, who examines both the theoretical foundations and translation procedures of ecotourism terms in bilingual systems and emphasizes that accurate translation plays a critical role in cross-cultural and scholarly understanding. The incorporation of international and Uzbek scholarship reflects the growing interdisciplinary nature of this field.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International linguists ^[2] provide a framework for analyzing word-formation processes (affixation, compounding, borrowing). According to Crystal ^[3], English dominates globally, which explains why most ecotourism terminology is borrowed rather than locally adapted. Uzbek researchers build upon these foundations. The interaction between structural morphology and translation studies is illustrated in Abdullayeva's research, where translation theories reveal modifications in ecotourism vocabulary between English and Uzbek, as well as the impact of translation strategies on meaning and usage. Fennell (2020), Honey (2019), and Weaver (2020) focus on the sustainable and ethical aspects of tourism in global studies, establishing semantic categories such as sustainability, conservation, and community involvement. Mirzayorova (2025), based at Aniq va Ijtimoiy Fanlar Universiteti, extends these ideas by providing a comparative analysis of English and Uzbek language use in concepts such as responsible travel, nature-based tourism, and community-based ecotourism, which form the foundation of sustainable tourism discourse and influence lexical choices in both languages ^[6].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Many English ecotourism terms are formed through affixation: sustain → sustainable → sustainability ^[2], as well as ecology → ecological → ecologically. In Uzbek, similar processes include ekologiya → ekologik, turizm → turistik, and barqaror → barqarorlik.

Research by Abdullayeva shows that affixation is not equally productive across languages; in Uzbek, native suffixes such as -lik are frequently used to express abstract qualities ^[1].

Compounding is also a key word-formation process in both languages, for example eco + tourism → ecotourism and biodiversity + conservation → biodiversity conservation.

English compounds tend to be structurally compact, whereas Uzbek often uses phrase-based constructions such as tabiat muhofazasi, reflecting the structural difference between agglutinative (Uzbek) and analytic (English) language types.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Comparative studies highlight morphological compounding as a central feature of ecotourism terminology ^[1]. The borrowing of ecotourism terms in Uzbek is not merely lexical transfer but a strategic response to the global dominance of English in environmental sciences, ensuring international compatibility while supporting the development of national terminology. Direct borrowing and transliteration include examples such as Booking → Buking, Voucher → Voucher, and Ecotourism → Ekoturizm, while phonological and morphological adaptation can be seen in Ecotourist → Ekoturist and Agritourism → Agroturizm. Hybrid formations combine borrowed roots with native suffixes, as in Ekoturizm + -shunos → Ekoturizmshunos. The rapid influx of English terms creates "eco-terminological lacunas," where direct native equivalents are lacking, and scholars emphasize that borrowing must be balanced with national linguistic identity to preserve cultural nuance while maintaining global intelligibility.

Table 1: Ecotourism Terminology: English Terms, Uzbek Borrowings, and Native/Calque Equivalents

English Term	Uzbek Borrowing (Phonetic/Direct)	Native/Calque Alternative
Sustainable	Sasteynabl (rare)	Barqaror (native/standard)
Nature Tourism	Neycher turizm (avoided)	Tabiat turizmi (calque)
Carbon Footprint	Karbon futprint (rare)	Uglerod izlari (calque)
Tour Operator	Turoperator	Sayohat tashkilotchisi

As noted by Abdullayeva, the preference for borrowing versus calquing often depends on the term's "tightness"; while English favors creative neologisms and blends (e.g., ecotel), Uzbek often relies on more descriptive phrases or direct transliterations for technical precision. This borrowing is common in both local and international research ^[3].

In response to lexicographic needs, Uzbek scholars emphasize the necessity of achieving a balance between global intelligibility and national linguistic identity. Word-formation models can be observed from both regional and global perspectives. In English, word formation follows structured morphological patterns in which suffixes are arranged sequentially after base morphemes. These include prefixation (e.g., eco-, bio-), suffixation (e.g., -ism, -ity, -al), as well as compounding and conversion. Bauer notes that these mechanisms are highly productive in English ^[2].

In contrast, Uzbek word formation exhibits different tendencies:

- suffixed forms such as -lik are commonly used to form abstract nouns;
- multi-word expressions are frequent;
- and calqued compounds (literal translations rather than portmanteaus) are preferred.

Local morphological studies, including analyses of suffixes such as -izm in terminological formation ^[7], demonstrate that suffixation significantly influences both vocabulary and semantics, which can also be applied to ecotourism terminology. The conceptual meaning of ecotourism terminology is generally precise; however, polysemy (multiple meanings) complicates translation and interpretation. Studies on tourism terminology ^[1] indicate that polysemy introduces variation between English and Uzbek equivalents, making translation and lexicographic description more challenging.

Cultural adaptation also plays a crucial role. Usmonova (2022) highlights that beyond morphology and syntax, meaning is shaped by cultural context ^[8], thus adding an essential semantic dimension to structural analysis. Issues of inconsistency and borrowing remain significant. Excessive reliance on borrowed terms may lead to inconsistency and reduced linguistic independence unless such terms are properly adapted. Uzbek researchers stress the importance of developing standardized bilingual dictionaries and terminological corpora. Yusupova (2023) further emphasizes that lexicographic resources are essential for standardizing ecotourism vocabulary, particularly for education, translation, and international academic collaboration ^[10].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, ecotourism nomenclature represents a linguistically rich and conceptually complex system shaped by both global ecological discourse and local linguistic practices. While international scholars provide theoretical frameworks for word formation and interdisciplinary, Uzbek researchers contribute comparative insights and highlight challenges related to translation and standardization ^{[1], [4]}.

The future development of ecotourism terminology in Uzbekistan depends on sustained collaboration between linguists and domain specialists, with a focus on lexicographic standardization and the creation of culturally appropriate terms.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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